

Entire Atmosphere Global Model (EAGLE)

Brief description

The EAGLE consists of two modules: HAMMONIA (Hamburg Model of the Neutral and Ionized Atmosphere) for the lower atmosphere and GSM TIP (Global Self-consistent Model of the Thermosphere, Ionosphere and Protonosphere) for the upper atmosphere. The EAGLE main components and data flow are illustrated in Figure 1.

1.1 Module HAMMONIA

The HAMMONIA is a revised version of the general atmospheric circulation model ECHAM5, in which the upper boundary is raised to ~ 200-250 km. HAMMONIA also includes the MOZART3 package to describe chemical process. For the proper description of the thermospheric process the model was extended to include radiation heating due to the absorption of extreme solar ultraviolet radiation, cooling due to infrared radiation in case of local thermodynamic equilibrium violation, molecular diffusion, Joule heating and ion drag. The chemical module was supplemented by ion chemistry, which enables the production of nitrogen oxides by different precipitating energetic particles.

The system of hydro-thermodynamic equations in the model is solved by the spectral method with triangular truncation T63, which approximately corresponds to a horizontal resolution of 2x2 degrees in latitude and longitude. Vertically, the model contains 119 levels with a thickness of layers varying from 600 m in the upper troposphere to 3 km in the mesosphere and 8 km in the thermosphere. The applied time step is 3 minutes for dynamics. To use the model in the free running mode, the temperature of the ocean surface, the distribution of sea ice, surface fluxes or the surface concentration of greenhouse and ozone-depleting gases, the spectral flux of solar radiation, ionization rates, and a number of other parameters should be prescribed. To simulate specific events (atmospheric phenomena and manifestations of space weather), the use of assimilation of meteorological fields is advised. A detailed description of the model can be found in (Schmidt et al. 2006; Meraner et al., 2016).

1.2. Module GSM TIP.

The Global Self-consistent Model of the Thermosphere, Ionosphere and Protonosphere (GSM TIP) (Namgaladze et al., 1988, 1991; Korenkov et al., 1998) was developed in the WD IZMIRAN (West Department of Pushkov Institute of Terrestrial Magnetism, Ionosphere and Radio wave propagation of the Russian Academy of Sciences). The model calculates time-dependent global three-dimensional structure of the near-Earth space environment from 80 km to 15 Earth radii, in particular: (1) the distributions of temperature, composition and velocity vector of neutral gas; (2) the density, temperature, and velocity vectors of atomic and molecular ions and electrons; (3) the two-dimensional distribution of electric field potential, both of a dynamo and magnetospheric origin. The GSM TIP model consists of three main modules describing thermosphere, ionosphere, and the electric fields. In the thermospheric module global distributions of the neutral gas temperature, N_2 , O_2 , O , NO , $N(^4S)$, and $N(^2D)$ concentrations as well as three-dimensional neutral winds are calculated in the 80-526 km layer using spherical geomagnetic coordinate system. In the vertical dimension, the thermospheric code uses 30 layers, with each layer approximately equal to a half thickness of scale height. The vertical resolution is 3 km near the lower boundary and increases to 40 km at 526 km altitude. Ionospheric module calculates three-dimensional density of the N_2^+ , O_2^+ , and NO^+ , ion temperature and velocities in the 80- 526 km layer including D, E, F using spherical geomagnetic coordinate system. In the F2 region and protonosphere, the densities, temperatures, and vector velocities of atomic (O^+ , H^+) ions and electrons are calculated in the magnetic dipole coordinate system from a base altitude 175 km in the northern hemisphere to 175 km in the southern hemisphere or to a maximum distance of 15 Earth's radii (in case of

open geomagnetic field lines). In this case, the calculation of the atomic ions does not require the upper boundary condition. The ionospheric module has variable spatial steps along the magnetic field lines. Additionally, the model provides the two-dimensional electric field potential distribution for thermospheric dynamo and magnetospheric origin (Klimenko et al. 2006, 2007).

All model equations are solved by the finite difference method. The Earth's magnetic field is approximated by the central dipole. Thus, discrepancy of geographical and geomagnetic axes is taken into account. The solution of the full system of equations of the model is performed numerically on a global grid with resolutions of 5° in latitude and 5° in longitude as specified in the spherical geomagnetic coordinate system; the time step is 1 min. The transformations between all coordinate systems in the model are given by standard equations. The model inputs are: (1) the solar EUV and UV irradiance in the spectral range (10–1760 Å); (2) the precipitating electron fluxes and energies; (3) the amplitudes and spatial distribution of Region 1 field aligned currents or a cross-polar cap potential difference and Region 2 (R2) field-aligned currents.

GSM TIP uses Nusinov (1992) model solar X-ray and EUV spectra (10-1050 Å). The cross-polar cap potential difference was set at geomagnetic latitudes $\pm 75^\circ$, and R2 field-aligned currents (FAC), j_2 , at geomagnetic latitudes ± 70 . In the base versions, the empirical models by Zhang and Paxton (2008) or Vorobjev and Yagodkina (2008) are used for high-energy particle precipitation. The energy and flux of precipitating electrons depend on a three-hour Kp-index in the first model, and on a one-minute AL-index in the second model correspondingly.

The GSM TIP was described in detail by Namgaladze et al. (1988, 1991), Korenkov et al. (1998), and model modifications were presented in Klimenko et al. (2006, 2007, 2011a), Bessarab and Korenkov (2011), Korenkov et al. (2017). The GSM TIP has been used to study the thermosphere-ionosphere system response to the dynamic forcing from below (Karpov and Bessarab, 2008; Namgaladze et al., 2009; Klimenko et al., 2011b, 2012; Bessarab et al., 2012).

1.3. Coupling

To connect the two modules, a software interface has been developed that prepares the fields of both models for transmission to each other in the overlap area and allows synchronization of parallel (HAMMONIA) and sequential (GSM TIP) calculations. HAMMONIA provides neutral temperature and wind fields in the region of 80–120 km, the importance of which is determined by the activity of gravitational waves, air density, O, N, and NO concentration at 80 km, and GSM TIP returns the results of ion-neutral interactions (Joule heating and ion friction) in the region of 80-250 km. A detailed description and examples of the use of the new model can be found in (Klimenko et al., 2019 a,b).

Figure 1. Main components and data flow of the EAGLE model.

References

- Bessarab, F.S., Yu.N. Korenkov, M.V. Klimenko, V.V. Klimenko, I.V. Karpov, K.G. Ratovsky, M.A. Chernigovskaya. *Modeling the effect of Sudden Stratospheric Warming within the thermosphere-ionosphere system. J. Atmos. Solar-Terr. Phys.*, 2012, 90–91, 77–85.
- Feshchenko, E.Yu., Maltsev, Yu.P. *Relations of the polar cap voltage to the geophysical activity, in: Proc. XXVI Annual Seminar "Physics of Auroral Phenomena", February 25–28, 2003, PGI KSC RAS, Apatity, Russia, 2003, 59–61.*
- Klimenko, M.V., Klimenko, V.V., Bryukhanov, V.V. *Numerical simulation of the electric field and zonal current in the Earth's ionosphere: the dynamo field and equatorial electrojet, Geomagn. Aeron.* 2006, 46(4), 457–466, doi:10.1134/S0016793206040074.
- Klimenko, M.V., V.V. Klimenko, and V.V. Bryukhanov. *Numerical modeling of the equatorial electrojet UT-variation on the basis of the model GSM TIP. Adv. Radio Sci.*, 2007, 5, 385–392.
- Klimenko, M.V., V.V. Klimenko, K.G. Ratovsky, L.P. Goncharenko, Y. Sahai, P.R. Fagundes, R. de Jesus, A.J. de Abreu, and A.M. Vesnin. *Numerical modeling of ionospheric effects in the middle- and low-latitude F region during geomagnetic storm sequence of 9–14 September 2005. Radio Sci.*, 2011, 46, RS0D03, doi:10.1029/2010RS004590.
- Klimenko, M., V. Klimenko, F. Bessarab, T. Sukhodolov, P. Vasiliev, I. Karpov, Y. Korenkov, I. Zakharenkova, B. Funke, E. Rozanov, *Tropical lower thermospheric anomalies and identification of the mechanisms responsible for January 2009 sudden stratospheric warming influence on low latitude ionosphere (2019b), J. Space Weather Space Clim.* 9 A39, doi: 10.1051/swsc/2019037
- Korenkov, Yu.N., Klimenko, V.V., Förster, M., et al. *Calculated and observed ionospheric parameters for a Magion-2 passage and EISCAT data on July 31, 1990, J. Geophys. Res.* 1998, 103(A7), 14697–14710.
- Korenkov, Yu.N., F. S. Bessarab, V. V. Klimenko, and M. V. Klimenko. *Effect of the Spatial and Temporal Distribution of Molecular Ions in the Ionospheric E-Field on the Behavior of NmF2 during the Geomagnetic Storm of March 17–23, 2015. Russian J. Phys. Chem B.* 2017, Vol. 11, No. 5, pp. 859–872.
- Meraner, K., H. Schmidt, E. Manzini, B. Funke, and A. Gardini (2016), *Sensitivity of simulated mesospheric transport of nitrogen oxides to parameterized gravity waves, J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.*, 121, 12,045–12,061, doi:10.1002/2016JD025012.
- Namgaladze, A.A., Yu.N. Koren'kov, V.V. Klimenko, I.V. Karpov, F.S. Bessarab, V.A. Surotkin, T.A. Glushenko, and N.M. Naumova, *Global model of the thermosphere-ionosphere-protonosphere system. Pure and Applied Geophysics (PAGEOPH)*, 1988, 127(2/3), 219–254.
- Namgaladze, A.A., Korenkov, Yu.N., Klimenko, V.V., et al. *Numerical modelling of the thermosphere-ionosphere-protonosphere system, J. Atmos. Terr. Phys.* 1991, 53, 1113–1124.
- Nusinov A.A. *Proceeding of the Workshop on the Solar Electromagnetic Radiation Study for Solar Cycle 22. Space Environment Laboratory. NOAA ERL. P. 354-359. July. 1992.*
- Vorobjev V.G., Yagodkina O.I. *Empirical model of auroral precipitation power during substorms // J. Atm. Solar-Terr. Phys.* 2008, V. 70, P. 654-662.
- Schmidt, H., G. P. Brasseur, M. Charron, E. Manzini, M. A. Giorgetta, T. Diehl, V. I. Fomichev, D. Kinnison, D. Marsh, and S. Walters (2006), *The HAMMONIA chemistry climate model: Sensitivity of the mesopause region to the 11-year solar cycle and CO2 doubling, J. Clim.*, 19(16), 3903–3931, doi:10.1175/JCLI3829.1.
- Zhang, Y., Paxton, L.J. *An empirical Kp-dependent global auroral model based on TIMED/GUVI FUV data, J. Atmos. Solar-Terr. Phys.* 2008, 70, 1231–1242.